

Impact of a pharmaceutical algorithm on patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms: A pre-post intervention study

María Puig-Moltó^a, Blanca Lumbreras^{a,b,*}, Juan Manuel Mendive^c, Elsa López-Pintor^{b,d}

^a Department of Public Health, History of Science and Gynecology, Miguel Hernandez University, San Juan de Alicante, Spain

^b CIBER of Epidemiology and Public Health, CIBERESP, Spain

^c La Mina Primary Health Care Academic Centre, Sant Adrià de Besòs (Barcelona) Catalan Institut of Health (ICS), University of Barcelona, Spain.

^d Department of Engineering, Area of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Technology, Miguel Hernandez University, San Juan de Alicante, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Community pharmacy₁
Gastroesophageal reflux₂
Functional dyspepsia₃
Upper-gastrointestinal symptoms₄
Epigastric symptoms₅
Retrosternal symptoms₆
Pharmaceutical professional Service₇

ABSTRACT

Objective: To evaluate the algorithm impact on the upper gastrointestinal patients' symptoms (PROMs) and satisfaction with pharmaceutical care received (PREMs).

Methods: The algorithm was previously developed by clinicians and pharmacists, through a pre-post intervention study in Spain (June–October 2022). We included 1221 patients who were seeking advice and/or medication for symptoms at 134 community pharmacies. Patients' sociodemographic and clinical variables were assessed at baseline and were classified in accordance with the Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease Impact Scale (GIS) into patients with either epigastric, retrosternal or overlapping symptoms. Interventions included medical referral; education on healthy habits; prescription of an OTC treatment or a non-pharmacologic prescription. Fourteen days later, patients were assessed through: a) the change on the GIS score, and b) patients' satisfaction with pharmaceutical care received.

Results: Most patients reported overlapping symptoms (660, 54.0%), 171 (14.0%) reported epigastric symptoms and 390 (32.0%) retrosternal symptoms. Patients with epigastric symptoms did not show a difference in the GIS score after the intervention while those with retrosternal symptoms and those with overlapping symptoms did (mean 1.09 (4.28 SD), $p < 0.001$ and mean 3.18 (6.01 SD), $p < 0.001$, respectively). Patients who received education on healthy habits and those with a prescription of a pharmacological treatment (antacids in monotherapy and alginates-antiacids) showed an increase in the GIS score. Patients' satisfaction with pharmaceutical care received was over 99.2% of sample.

Conclusion: Implementation of the upper-gastrointestinal symptoms algorithm in Community pharmacies had a positive impact on patients' symptoms, quality of life, and satisfaction with pharmaceutical care received.

1. Introduction

Gastroesophageal Reflux (GER) and Functional Dyspepsia (FD) are common disorders in the general population with an estimated pooled prevalence of 15% for GER and 21% for FD, although this can vary by geographic area. (Eusebi et al., 2018a, 2018b; Ford et al., 2015).

GER is commonly associated with symptoms such as heartburn and regurgitation in the retrosternal or esophageal area. According to the IV Rome criteria, FD is associated with postprandial fullness, early satiation, pain and burning in the epigastric area. (Rome IV Criteria, 2024). Nevertheless, according to the literature, symptoms of FD and GER can overlap (Choung et al., 2012; de Bortoli et al., 2018; Rey et al., 2006).

The diagnosis of these conditions, however, remains unclear due to the lack of evidence regarding the pathophysiological mechanisms that could contribute to this overlap (Geeraerts et al., 2020). We carried out a previous cross-sectional study on 1360 patients of whom, 54.3% reported overlapping symptoms (Puig-Moltó et al., 2023). These patients had poorer health outcomes and frequently used more chronic medications than patients with either retrosternal or epigastric symptoms.

Pharmacologic treatments available to date for the management of FD have only been shown to be of limited efficacy (Bosman et al., 2023), and in patients with GERD empirical PPI treatment is usually initiated. Given that these disorders frequently coexist, it is relevant to distinguish between FD, GER and FD-GER overlap, to establish the most suitable

* Corresponding author at: Department of Public Health, History of Science and Gynecology, Miguel Hernandez University, San Juan de Alicante, Spain.
E-mail address: blumbreras@umh.es (B. Lumbreras).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2024.107885>

Received 15 November 2023; Received in revised form 31 January 2024; Accepted 2 February 2024

Available online 3 February 2024

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management strategy in each case (Eusebi et al., 2018a, 2018b).

Patients with gastrointestinal symptoms often turn to community pharmacies for over the counter (OTC) treatments or advice on how to alleviate their symptoms. Educational interventions related with daily habits, such as smoking, diet and physical activity, and also increasing adherence to treatment have shown an impact on the improvement of patients' symptoms (Goh et al., 2021; MacFarlane, 2018). Given the frequency of patients with overlapping symptoms, the development of an algorithm to support community pharmacists in the management of these patients would improve their symptomatology and quality of health.

The Spanish Society of Community Pharmacy (SEFAC) and the Spanish Society of General Practitioners (SEMERGEN) have developed a joint algorithm to manage patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms in the community pharmacy. We aimed in this study, to manage patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms in the community pharmacy.

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have recommended the inclusion of well-defined Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) and Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREMs) for adequate evaluation of treatment efficacy in patients with FD and GER (Bosman et al., 2023; Eusebi et al., 2018a, 2018b; Goh et al., 2021; MacFarlane, 2018; Puig-Moltó et al., 2023). Thus, the inclusion of PROMs and PREMs in the evaluation of such an algorithm, will improve the pharmacist's knowledge on the best strategy in the management of patients with gastrointestinal symptoms.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of an algorithm on the management of patients with upper gastrointestinal symptoms through the assessment of PROMs and PREMs in the community pharmacy in real-world data.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

A pre-post-intervention study was conducted to evaluate the impact of a professional pharmaceutical service on patients with upper gastrointestinal symptoms who were attended in Spanish community pharmacies, June–October 2022 (López-Pintor et al., 2022).

2.2. Study population

Participation was offered to community pharmacists throughout the national territory. In Spain, pharmacies are private healthcare institutions, but they work as well for the public healthcare system.

Patients older than 18 years old who visited community pharmacies seeking advice for upper gastrointestinal symptoms or requesting OTC treatment for these symptoms were included. Patients with high-risk pregnancies or those requesting treatment for someone else were excluded from the study.

The sample size calculation has been previously described (López-Pintor et al., 2022).

2.3. Recruitment procedure

- Community pharmacists:

Participation in the study was voluntary. The Spanish Society for Community Pharmacy (SEFAC) and Miguel Hernandez University (UMH) asked a random sample of community pharmacists to voluntarily participate in the study. We adjusted the sample size to the population of all different Spanish regions, until the required sample size was reached. Initially, 411 community pharmacists participated and finally, 134 were included from 23 Spanish provinces. To achieve the sample size calculated, we estimated that each pharmacist participant had to include a

minimum of 5 patients.

The enrolled pharmacists received some training before the study started. They received three training videos including information on the study methodology, objectives and procedures. The study monitor phoned the pharmacists to confirm that all the information was understood and to clarify any doubts.

- Patients:

Community pharmacists invited those patients who met the inclusion criteria. They were explained the entire process of the study and were given an information sheet. Once patients agreed to participate, they signed the informed agreement as a prerequisite. The patients were classified with an identification code: CA-III-PN (CA: autonomous community (Spanish region) code; III: investigators' initials; PN and N stands for the participant number).

2.4. Procedure of the study and data collection

The study included two visits: at baseline and 14 days later.

1) Baseline visit: the community pharmacists collected the socio-demographic and clinical information, which it is described in the Fig. 1.

In accordance with patients' clinical information, community pharmacists implemented any of the four different interventions described in the algorithm previously published (López-Pintor et al., 2022): a) medical referral; b) health habits education; c) prescription of an OTC treatment (alginates in combination with antacids, antacid monotherapy or PPI), and d) non-pharmacologic prescriptions (nutraceutical treatment, plant-based treatment and probiotics).

2) Follow-up visit.

The study monitor interviewed patients by phone 14 days after the baseline visit to assess the outcomes of the interventions. The description of the variables is included in the Appendix A.

2.5. Data analysis plan

A structured database was designed with the study variables. First, the pharmacist collected the information and uploaded it to the database, second, the external monitor evaluated all the information, called the patient after 14 days and proceeded to complete the variable database related to the follow-up visit. Only the external monitor and the principal researcher had access to the database. The statistical analysis was carried out with IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 27.0. Armonk, NY, USA: IBM Corp.

Data were analyzed and presented in descriptive form using absolute and relative frequencies with the 95% confidence interval. The test X² was used for the relation between categorical variables. For the continuous variables the Kolmogorov Smirnov test was used to analyze the normality, and then the non-parametric tests were used to analyze the significance. The GIS questionnaire responses were measured using a four-point Likert scale, and then a score is calculated, giving a number between 1 and 4. *p*-value <0.05 is considered significant.

All the analysis were carried out regarding to the patient classification: patients with epigastric symptoms, retrosternal symptoms and overlapping symptoms. Analysis of the impact of the pharmaceutical interventions was performed using the difference in the overall mean score on the GIS impact scale before and after the interventions. A statistically significant difference was considered an improvement in symptoms and quality of life.

2.6. Ethic approval statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The protocol has been approved by the Ethic Committee of Hospital Sant Joan d'Alacant (code: 19/335 Tut) and was previously classified as No Post-Marketing-Observational Study "No-EPA" by the

Fig. 1. Flowchart describing the patients included in the study.

Table 1

Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the study sample, stratified by patients' symptomatology (epigastric, retrosternal, and overlapping), among individuals visiting Spanish community pharmacies from June to October 2022.

Variables N	Total (1221)	Epigastric symptoms (171)	Retrosternal symptoms (390)	Overlapping symptoms (660)	p- value
Sex (%)					0.886
Female	726(59.5)	100(58.5)	229(58.7)	397(60.2)	
Male	495(40.5)	71(41.5)	161(41.3)	263(39.8)	
Age (years) (mean, SD)	49.59(16.52)	48.47(16.06)	50.89(16.91)	49.11(16.39)	0.338
BMI (kg/m ²) (mean, SD)	26.21(4.31)	26.48(4.29)	26.11(4.32)	26.19(4.31)	0.652
Reason for consultation (%)					0.200
Seeking treatment advice for the symptoms	476(39.0)	70(40.9)	137(35.1)	269(40.8)	
Requesting over-the counter medication	699(57.2)	98(57.3)	238(61.0)	363(55.0)	
Both	46(3.8)	3(1.8)	15(3.8)	28(4.2)	
Requested over-the counter medication (%)					0.003
Antacid monotherapy	512(69.7)	89(89.0)	174(69.9)	249(64.5)	
Alginates in combination with antacids	97(13.2)	4(4.0)	31(12.4)	62(16.1)	
PPIs	75(10.2)	5(5.0)	26(10.4)	44(11.4)	
Educational level (%)					0.012
No studies	57(4.7)	7(4.1)	17(4.4)	33(5.0)	
Primary education	288(23.6)	53(31.0)	75(19.2)	160(24.2)	
Secondary education	426(34.9)	50(29.2)	166(42.6)	210(31.8)	
University education	423(34.6)	58(33.9)	123(31.5)	242(36.7)	
NS/NC	27(2.2)	3(1.8)	9(2.3)	15(2.3)	
Frequency of physical activity (%)					0.678
Every day	339(27.8)	50(29.2)	113(29.0)	176(26.7)	
Once or twice/a week	373(30.5)	54(31.6)	116(29.7)	203(30.8)	
3-5 times/a month	232(19.0)	24(14.0)	76(19.5)	132(20.0)	
Never	277(22.7)	43(25.1)	85(21.8)	149(22.6)	
Smoking habits (%)					0.161
Smokers	280(22.9)	51(29.8)	78(20.0)	151(22.9)	
Ex-smokers	312(25.6)	39(22.8)	105(26.9)	168(25.5)	
Non-smokers	629(51.5)	81(47.4)	207(53.1)	341(51.7)	
Presence of alarm criteria (%)	769(63.0)	100(58.5)	219(56.2)	450(68.2)	< 0.001
Use of treatment before visiting the pharmacy (%)					< 0.001
Prescribed	232(29.3)	22(21.2)	70(29.8)	140(30.8)	
Over-the counter medication	486(61.3)	82(78.8)	139(59.1)	265(58.4)	
Both	75(9.5)	0(0.0)	26(11.1)	49(10.8)	
Previous use of antacid monotherapy (%)	314(25.7)	53(31.0)	93(23.8)	168(25.5)	0.199
Previous use of alginates in combination with antacids (%)	171(14.0)	16(9.4)	52(13.3)	103(15.6)	0.099
Previous use of PPIs	395(32.4)	38(22.2)	117(30.0)	240(36.4)	0.001

BMI: Body Mass Index; PPIs: Proton Pump Inhibitors.

For categorical variables p-value was calculated by the weighted X² test; for continuous variables p-value was calculated by t-student.

Spanish Agency of Medicines and Medical Devices (AEMPS).

3. Results

3.1. Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the study sample

We collected data from 1360 patients at the baseline visit and 1221 (89.8%) patients were interviewed 14 days later at the followed-up visit. Therefore, 139 of 1360 (10.2%) patients were lost of follow-up: 18 of 189 (9.5%) patients with epigastric symptoms, 43 of 433 (9.9%) patients with retrosternal symptoms, and 78 of 738 (10.6%) of patients with overlapping symptoms.

Of the 1221 patients who completed the follow-up, 171 (14.0%) patients reported epigastric symptoms, 390 (32.0%) patients had retrosternal symptoms and 660 (54.0%) patients had overlapping symptoms (Fig. 1). Participants were predominantly female (726, 59.5%), mean age was 49.59 (SD 16.52) years old, and mean BMI was 26.21 (SD 4.31). Most patients attended the community pharmacy to request OTC medication (699, 57.2%), and antacid monotherapy was the most common treatment requested (512, 69.7%) (Table 1).

Patients with overlapping symptoms (450, 68.2%) were more likely to present alarm criteria than patients with epigastric symptoms (100, 58.5%) and those with retrosternal symptoms (219, 56.2%) ($p < 0.001$). Patients with epigastric symptoms were more likely to request antacid monotherapy (89, 89.0%) than patients with retrosternal symptoms (174, 69.9%) and those with overlapping symptoms (249, 64.5%); in addition, patients with overlapping symptoms (62, 16.1%) were more likely to request alginates in combination with antacids than patients

with epigastric symptoms (4, 4.0%) and those with retrosternal symptoms (31, 12.4%). Patients with epigastric symptoms (5, 5.0%) were less likely to request PPIs than patients with retrosternal symptoms (26, 10.4%) and those with overlapping symptoms (44, 11.4%) ($p = 0.003$) (Table 1).

Patients with epigastric symptoms (82, 78.8%) were more likely to use an OTC treatment before the inclusion in the study than patients with retrosternal symptoms (139, 59.1%) and those with overlapping symptoms (265, 58.4%) ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

3.2. Description of the interventions

Most patients received two interventions (695, 56.9%).

The interventions focused on providing patients with health habits education (877, 71.8%), pharmacological treatment indication (896, 73.4%), non-pharmacological prescription (206, 16.9%) and 180 (14.7%) patients were referred to their general practitioner (GP). Patients with overlapping symptoms (129, 19.5%) were more frequently referred to their GP than patients with epigastric symptoms (12, 7.0%) and those with retrosternal symptoms (39, 10%) ($p < 0.001$). Out of the 180 patients who were referred to their GP, 63 (35%) attended to the medical appointment and there were not differences according to the type of symptoms (0.876). Patients with epigastric symptoms were more likely to receive a pharmacologic treatment indication (137, 80.1%) than those with retrosternal symptoms (296, 75.9%) and those with overlapping symptoms (463, 70.2%) ($p = 0.013$) (Table 2).

Table 2

Description of various pharmaceutical interventions and their impact on GERD Impact Scale Scores (pre, post, post-pre) in patients visiting Spanish community pharmacies, stratified by symptomatology (epigastric, retrosternal, and overlapping), during June–October 2022.

Interventions	N (%)	<i>p</i> value ¹	GERD impact scale (pre) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post-pre) (mean, SD)	<i>p</i> value ²
Medical referral		< 0.001				
Epigastric symptoms	12/171 (7.0)		28.33 (3.96)	30.17 (4.86)	1.83 (4.53)	0.921
Retrosternal symptoms	39/390 (10.0)		27.41 (5.54)	27.85 (6.44)	0.44 (6.02)	0.075
Overlapping symptoms	129/660 (19.5)		20.47 (6.48)	24.33 (6.58)	3.87 (6.53)	0.064
Total	180/1221 (14.7)		22.49 (6.93)	25.48 (6.70)	2.99 (6.44)	0.115
Health habits education		0.309				
Epigastric symptoms	124/171 (72.5)		30.57 (3.24)	32.59 (3.55)	2.02 (3.89)	0.834
Retrosternal symptoms	269/390 (69.0)		30.67 (4.72)	31.81 (4.56)	1.14 (4.27)	< 0.001
Overlapping symptoms	484/660 (73.3)		24.16 (6.84)	27.55 (6.22)	3.39 (5.82)	< 0.001
Total	877/1221 (71.8)		27.06 (6.67)	29.57 (5.88)	2.5 (5.24)	< 0.001
Pharmacologic treatment indication		0.013				
Epigastric symptoms	137/171 (80.1)		30.79 (3.16)	32.61 (3.54)	1.82 (3.68)	0.939
Retrosternal symptoms	296/390 (75.9)		31.06 (4.64)	32.08 (4.38)	1.02 (4.14)	< 0.001
Overlapping symptoms	463/660 (70.2)		24.85 (6.61)	27.92 (6.17)	3.08 (6.04)	< 0.001
Total	896/1221 (73.4)		27.81 (6.37)	30.01 (5.71)	2.21 (5.24)	< 0.001
Non-pharmacologic prescription		0.007				
Epigastric symptoms	19/171 (11.1)		31 (2.54)	31.63 (4.06)	0.63 (3.65)	0.665
Retrosternal symptoms	56/390 (14.4)		30.27 (4.65)	31.57 (4.56)	1.3 (3.62)	0.049
Overlapping symptoms	131/660 (19.8)		23.82 (6.4)	27.15 (6.23)	3.33 (5.73)	0.026
Total	206/1221 (16.9)		26.24 (6.53)	28.77 (6.02)	2.53 (5.16)	0.056

p value¹: comparison of each intervention within each symptom group (epigastric, retrosternal, overlapping). *p*-value was calculated by the weighted χ^2 test.

p value²: comparison of GERD impact scale score pre and post of each intervention within each symptom group (epigastric, retrosternal, overlapping). *p*-value was calculated by t-Student.

3.3. Clinical impact of interventions on patients' symptoms and quality of life

Mean score in the GIS questionnaire before the intervention was 27.32 (SD 6.58) and after the intervention median was 29.65 (SD 5.92), with a statistically significant difference of 2.33 points (SD 5.32), $p < 0.001$ (Table 3).

Patients with epigastric symptoms did not show a difference in the GIS score after receiving the intervention. Patients with retrosternal symptoms and those with overlapping symptoms were found to have statistically significant difference before and after the intervention (median 1.09 (SD 4.28), $p < 0.001$ and median 3.18 (SD 6.01), $p < 0.001$, respectively)(Table 3).

Those patients who were referred to their general practitioner did not show a significant change in the GIS scale ($p = 0.115$) and there was no difference regardless of whether patients attended the medical appointment. Patients who received an intervention centered on health habit education were found to have an increase in the GIS score after the intervention (mean difference post-pre GIS 2.5 (SD 3.89), $p < 0.001$). This significant change was found only in patients with retrosternal symptoms (mean 1.14 (SD 4.27), $p < 0.001$) and in those with overlapping symptoms (mean 0.39 (SD 5.82), $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

In relation to the intervention of pharmacologic treatment, patients with epigastric symptoms did not show a statistically significant change in the GIS score after the intervention ($p = 0.939$), in contrast with patients with retrosternal symptoms (mean difference post-pre GIS mean 1.02 (SD4.14) ($p < 0.001$) and those with overlapping symptoms (mean difference post-pre GIS 3.08 (SD 6.04)) ($p < 0.001$). Only patients with overlapping symptoms (mean difference post-pre GIS 3.33 (SD 5.73) ($p = 0.026$)) and retrosternal symptoms (mean difference post-pre GIS 1.3 (SD 3.62) ($p = 0.049$)) were found to have statistically changes in the GIS score after the non-pharmacologic prescription (Table 2).

Antacid in monotherapy was the most indicated treatment in the study sample (556, 45.5%). Treatment with alginates + antacids was more common indicated in patients with overlapping (163/660, 24.7%) and retrosternal symptoms (96, 24.6%) than in patients with epigastric symptoms (8, 4.7%) ($p < 0.001$). Antacid in monotherapy was more frequently indicated in patients with epigastric symptoms (122, 71.3%) than in patients with retrosternal symptoms (177, 45.4%) and in those with overlapping symptoms (257, 38.9%) ($p < 0.001$) (Table 4).

Patients with retrosternal symptoms, were found to have significant differences when they received a treatment with alginates-antacids (mean difference post-pre GIS 1.22 (SD 4.40)) ($p = 0.001$) and with antacids in monotherapy (mean difference post-pre GIS 0.79 (SD 3.94)) ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, patients with overlapping symptoms, were found to have significant differences when they received a treatment with alginates-antacids (mean difference post-pre GIS 4.11 (SD 6.47)) ($p = 0.001$) and with antacids in monotherapy (mean difference post-pre GIS 2.35 (SD 5.88)) ($p = 0.001$) (Table 4).

Table 3

Pre, post, and post-pre GERD Impact Scale Scores in patients attending Spanish community pharmacies, classified by symptom groups (epigastric, retrosternal, and overlapping), from June to October 2022.

Group of patients	GERD impact scale (pre) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post-pre) (mean, SD)	p value
Epigastric symptoms	30.73 (3.24)	32.61 (3.49)	1.88(3.82)	0.852
Retrosternal symptoms	30.79 (4.75)	31.89 (4.59)	1.09 (4.28)	<0.001
Overlapping symptoms	24.39 (6.75)	27.57 (6.30)	3.18 (6.01)	<0.001
Total	27.32 (6.58)	29.65 (5.92)	2.33 (5.32)	<0.001

p-value was calculated by t-student.

3.4. Impact of interventions on patients' satisfaction with the pharmaceutical care received (PREMs)

Overall, patients' satisfaction with the pharmaceutical care received was unanimous (99.2%). In addition, patients with epigastric symptoms (91.8%) and those with retrosternal symptoms (90.0%) were more likely to perceive improvement in their symptoms than patients with overlapping symptoms (77.4%), ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1, Appendix C).

4. Discussion

This study evaluated the impact of an algorithm designed for implementation in the community pharmacy, to manage patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms. We found that the symptomatology and quality of life of patients with retrosternal symptoms and those with overlapping symptoms improved after the pharmaceutical intervention. In contrast, patients with epigastric symptoms, did not show a significant difference in the GIS scale score after the community pharmacy intervention, regardless of the implemented intervention. This could be explained by the relatively small number of patients with epigastric symptoms in the study and by the lower severity of their symptoms. In contrast, patients with epigastric symptoms and those with retrosternal symptoms were more likely to perceive improvement in their symptoms than patients with overlapping symptoms.

Previous algorithms have been developed to support pharmacists in the management of patients with mild upper-gastrointestinal symptoms (Boardman et al., 2015) or GERD (Holtmann et al., 2011; Tytgat et al., 2008). These algorithms are mainly based on treatment with OTC medication and on highlighting alarming characteristics that indicate which patients should be referred directly to their GP. One of these previous algorithms (Tytgat et al., 2008) described as at the self-care level, OTC medications (antacids, alginate-antacids or low-dose PPIs) played a relevant role for relieving GERD symptoms, and if patients have persistent symptoms, the pharmacist should refer them to the primary care level. Another algorithm was focused on the use of PPI for GERD (Holtmann et al., 2011). The third algorithm, which supported pharmacists in the management of uncomplicated FD and reflux (Boardman et al., 2015), concluded that antacids and alginates were more suitable for the treatment of mild or occasional symptoms, whereas PPIs were more useful for the treatment of more serious or frequent symptoms. However, they include no other interventions. In contrast, our algorithm includes not only interventions related to pharmacological and medical referral but also to patients' education regarding healthy habits and non-pharmacological prescriptions.

In our study, the intervention centered on the referral of patients to their GP did not show a significant difference in the patients' GIS scale score. This could be partially explained by the fact that only 35% of patients who were referred to their GP attended the medical appointment. However, there were no differences between those patients who attended the medical appointment and those who did not. Interventions related to education on healthy habits and prescription of pharmacological and non-pharmacological prescription resulted in a significant improvement in both patients' symptomatology and quality of life. Education on healthy habits (toxic habits, diet and physical exercise) should always be incorporated in the management of patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms (MacFarlane, 2018), as is recommended by the American Gastroenterological Association (Yadlapati et al., 2022). Moreover, according to a previous study, education on healthy habits led to an increase in patients' knowledge and a decrease in the severity of GERD (Finley et al., 2009).

We found that antacids in monotherapy and alginates in combination with antacids were associated to an improvement in the patients' GIS scale score. A previous systematic review and meta-analysis also suggested that alginates be considered as a first-line treatment could be the mild symptoms of GERD (Leiman et al., 2017). PPIs did not show a significant difference in their GIS scale score, regardless the patient's

Table 4

Description of various pharmacological treatments and their impact on GERD Impact Scale Scores (pre, post, post-pre) in patients visiting Spanish community pharmacies, classified by symptom groups (epigastric, retrosternal, and overlapping), June–October 2022.

Treatments	N (%)	<i>p</i> -value ¹	GERD impact scale (pre) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post) (mean, SD)	GERD impact scale (post-pre) (mean, SD)	<i>p</i> -value ²
Alginates + antiacids						
		< 0.001				
Epigastric symptoms	8/171 (4.7)		30.50(3.02)	31.75(2.82)	1.25(2.82)	0.928
Retrosternal symptoms	96/390 (24.6)		30.14 (5.14)	31.35 (4.58)	1.22 (4.40)	0.001
Overlapping symptoms	163/660 (24.7)		23.60 (6.93)	27.71 (6.07)	4.11 (6.47)	0.001
Total	267/1221 (21.9)		26.16 (7.02)	29.14 (5.77)	2.99 (5.88)	0.002
Antiacids in monotherapy						
		< 0.001				
Epigastric symptoms	122/171(71.3)		31 (3.09)	32.70 (3.64)	1.70 (3.72)	0.420
Retrosternal symptoms	177/390 (45.4)		31.67(4.25)	32.46 (4.41)	0.79 (3.94)	< 0.001
Overlapping symptoms	257/660 (38.9)		25.63 (6.39)	27.98 (6.33)	2.35 (5.88)	0.001
Total	556/1221 (45.5)		28.73 (5.92)	30.44 (5.73)	1.71 (4.93)	< 0.001
PPIs						
		0.571				
Epigastric symptoms	7/171 (4.1)		27.43 (3.10)	32.14 (2.54)	4.71 (2.87)	0.061
Retrosternal symptoms	23/390 (5.9)		30.17 (4.66)	32.13 (2.83)	1.96 (4.53)	0.659
Overlapping symptoms	41/660 (6.2)		24.90 (5.96)	28.27 (5.67)	3.37 (4.63)	0.636
Total	71/1221 (5.8)		26.86 (5.82)	29.90 (5.02)	3.04 (4.49)	0.074

p value¹: comparison of the distribution of each pharmacological treatment within each symptom group (epigastric, retrosternal, overlapping). *p*-value was calculated by the weighted X² test.

p value²: comparison of GERD impact scale score pre and post of each pharmaceutical treatment within each symptom group (epigastric, retrosternal, overlapping). *p*-value was calculated by t-Student.

PPI, proton pump inhibitors.

symptoms. A meta-analysis described how patients with visceral hypersensitivity, or with unrelated acid exposure symptoms (as in patients with atypical symptoms such as dyspepsia) may have a lower response to treatment (Savarino et al., 2017).

To our knowledge, the impact of pharmaceutical interventions according to the patient's symptoms had not been evaluated to date. At baseline, patients with overlapping symptoms had a lower score in the GIS scale and presented alarming criteria more frequently than patients with epigastric or retrosternal symptoms, as in previous studies (Kaji et al., 2010; Lei et al., 2019). These patients showed a more pronounced improvement in their symptoms and quality of life after the interventions. The implementation of education on healthy habits and the indication of both pharmacological and non-pharmacological prescription may have contributed to this improvement. Patients with retrosternal symptoms showed a less marked improvement in their symptomatology and unlike patients with overlapping symptoms, the indication of non-pharmacological prescription did not contribute to this positive improvement. Non-pharmacological prescription, including nutraceutical treatment, plant based treatment or probiotics have shown benefits in some previous studies, but further evidence is needed to clarify the level of impact (Cheng and Ouwehand, 2020; Lacy et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2020). Given that the impact of the interventions varied according to the patient's main symptomatology, the use of the GIS scale as a tool to detect the different features of the patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms is an efficient way to personalize the strategies which need to be implemented in each patient.

We found that patients showed high levels of satisfaction with the attention received in the community pharmacy, higher than the range from 70 to 75% previously reported (Naser and Abu Sbeat, 2022; Pinto et al., 2014), and strengthened the role of the community pharmacy in the healthcare system. This percentage was lower with regard to the impact of the intervention on the patient's symptomatology, particularly among those with overlapping symptoms.

This study has several limitations. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic,

follow-up data collection after the 14-day intervention could not be face-to-face, but the study monitor evaluated the information received by the patients. Ten percent of the initially included patients were lost to follow-up. However, there were no differences in patient characteristics and similar percentages were lost in the three groups of patients regarding their symptoms. Another limitation could be that it does not consider other patient characteristics such as patient diseases and treatments that could affect the variables under study. However, patient use of gastrolesional medications and diagnosis of digestive disorders were recorded and examined to determine correlations and describe the population. We couldn't find any significant results.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the implementation of a pharmaceutical service based on an algorithm developed in consensus with general practitioners and gastroenterologists, showed a positive impact on the symptoms and quality of life of patients with upper-gastrointestinal symptoms. This improvement was significant in patients with retrosternal and overlapping symptoms, but not in patients with epigastric symptoms, probably due to the lower severity of their symptoms. Interventions based on health education as well as a pharmaceutical service prescription (alginates, antacids and other OTC prescriptions) contributed to these improvements. The inclusion in the study of PROMs and PREMs allowed the assessment of health outcomes such as patients' quality of life and symptomatology as well as patient satisfaction with the pharmaceutical care received.

Funding

This study was funded by Reckitt and supported by the Spanish Society of Family and Community Pharmacy (SEFAC). (Grant number: SEFAC 1.19). The funders were not involved in any aspect of the design of this study, management, analysis, and interpretation of data; writing

of the report or decision to submit it for publication.

Patient consent statement

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

María Puig-Moltó: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Blanca Lumbreras:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Juan Manuel Mendive:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Elsa López-Pintor:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

Elsa López-Pintor is a member of the SEFAC Scientific Committee. ELP and JMM has previously worked as an external advisor for Reckitt. However, this has not influenced any aspect of this research or the work presented.

All the authors have completed the ICMJE uniform disclosure form at www.icmje.org/coi_disclosure.pdf and declare: no support from any organisation for the submitted work; no financial relationships with any organizations that might have had an interest in the submitted work in the previous three years; no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Reckitt) and the Spanish Society of Family and Community Pharmacy (SEFAC) for funding and supporting this study and for the trust placed in our research team to design and carry it out. To Havas Medea Madrid for facilitating this research. To Professor Roger Jones, author of the GIS questionnaire, for his kindness and facilities in using the GIS questionnaire in this study. To Jessica Gorlin for language editing.

The authors would like to thank the following community pharmacist researchers for their excellent collaboration in the fieldwork of the project:

Adsuar Meseguer, Gonzalo Miguel; Alonso Pérez, Eva María; Amigó Avellán, María; Andraca Iturbe, Leire; Andrés Ferrándiz, Juan Miguel; Arenas Jové, Silvana; Argüello Uña, Sofía; Arrizabalaga Seminario, Ana; Aura Terol, Emilio; Azorín Brotons, Mar; Azorin Sanchez, María Dolores; Barbera Sabater, Elena; Barrio Vega, Noelia; Berengena Manchado, Manuel; Bernabéu Cerda, Julia; Bernabéu, Carla; Bertomeu Mullor, Marta; Brocal Pérez, Paula; Brú Hernández, Francisco; Buforn Guardiola, María; Cabrera Argudo, Isabel; Cabrera Flores, Andrés; Calero Vazquez, Javier; Calleja Bonifacio, Lorena; Campos Davó, Alicia; Cano Hernandez, Juan Antonio; Cantos Azorín, María Cristina; Casillas González, María; Centella Villatoro, María del Rosario; Centelles Forner, Santiago; Cerdà Blázquez, Veronica; Climent Benitez, Ignacio; Conejero Silvé, Ester; Corrales Lozano, Rocio; Cortés Fernández, María Esther; Costa Ballester, María José; de la Cuesta Barrutia, Jon; De la Fuente Cid, Ricardo; De la Ossa Rubio, Virgilio; De Moya Sagredo, Ana; Díaz Jiménez, Cristina; Díaz-Heredero Lozano, Elena; Doce Marcos, Patricia;

Dolz Martinez, Julia; Doménech Martí, Joan; Domingo Simón, Cristina; Eddaoui, Bahija; Egío Morales, Andrea; Farrero Gonzalez, Daniel; Fernández Gómez, Ignacio; Fernández Otero, María Dolores; Fernandez Paredes, Patricia; Ferrández Candela, Adelaida; Fontecha González, Gonzalo; Gago Casanova, Leticia; Galán Vázquez, María Pilar; Galindo Moreno, Alicia; Gallar Martínez, Víctor; García Albert, Carlos; García García, Pablo; García Gómez, Marina; García Martin, Diana; García Nicolas, Paloma; García Sevillano, Luis; García Urbano, Sonia; García-Moreno García-Pardo, Ana Irene; Gil Lázaro, Manuel Miguel; Gil Reina, Imelda; Gil Rodríguez, Juan; Giménez, Alejandra; Gómez Martínez, Jesús Carlos; Gómez Ramos, Aitana; González Barrios, Fernando; González Cantero, Raquel; González Carballo, Alba; González De La Portilla, Mónica; González Orts, Irene; González Pérez, Inmaculada; Granero Guijarro, Sandra; Griñán Pozo, José Javier; Guerrero García, Verónica; Guijarro Folgueral, Vicente; Haro Limiñana, Néstor; Hernández Gómez, Alejandro; Hernández Sánchez, Miguel; Herrero Rovira, Celia; Hidalgo Luna, Cristina; Hortelano Muñoz, Lali; Ibáñez, Andrea; Iborra Bou, José; Jaraiz Magariños, Irene; Jardim Espí, Idenia Marilin; Jimenez Moreno, Inmaculada; Jimenez Sabater, Angel; Jordá Sempere, Luis; Lahosa Tortajada, Gema; Lloret Pajares, David; Llusá Bayés, Ferrán; Lomo Casanueva, Julia; López Muñoz, Brígida; López Villodre, Pilar; López-Anguas Sánchez, Cristina; Lucas Suero, María Emma; Maestre Aguilar, Juan; Maiz Gregores, Helena; Malo Berrozpe, Ruth; Mancebo González, Ana Belén; Marín Ciria, Eva; Marín González, Patricia; Márquez de Prado Mena, Emilio; Martín Navarro, Esther; Martínez García, Olga María; Martínez García, Rosa María; Martínez Pardo, Pablo; Martínez Sánchez, Sara; Martínez Vicente, María Pilar; Martínez-Canales Calzadilla, Antonio Jesús; Mateos Sánchez, Mercedes; Megias Ruano, Marina; Mejido Ares, Yaiza María; Merelo de Barbera Sanroma, Alicia; Merino Lecea, Andrea; Migon Gonzaga, Laura; Miñarro Ortín, Jorge; Mira Sogorb, María; Miralles López, Francisca; Molina Laborda, Santiago; Monllor Corcoles, Blanca; Morcillo Cobo, José María; Moreno Ramos, Cristina María; Mugueta Jusué, María; Mulet Chorro, Cristina; Muñoz Cascajero, Adrián; Muñoz García, Cristina; Muñoz Monllor, Rocio; Mut Cholbi, Victor; Navarro Ribera, Patricia; Navarro Toral, Carmen; Nicolás Martínez, María José; Oliver Cazorla, Encar; Ortega Melero, Sagrario; Ortiz López, Oscar; Otero Coves, Adolfo; Palma López, Silvia; Páramo García, Rocio; Pardo Dávila, Sara María; Perea Tortosa, Carmen María; Pereira Gonzalez, Yanira; Pérez Alcaraz, Lorena; Pérez Belda, Elena; Pérez Martínez, Laura; Pérez Miguel, Alicia; Pérez Rabasco, Ana Isabel; Perseguer Torregrosa, Zeneida; Polanco Abad, María Luisa; Porta Barbero, Blanca; Puerta Beteta, María Cristina; Puerta Martínez, Rosa María; Puig Sapena, Ana María; Queiro Candal, Nerea; Ramón Oliver, Rosa María; Reolid Gisbert, Francisco; Rico Parreño, Carlos; Ripoll Tornel, José; Rodríguez Sampedro, Ana; Rodriguez Sánchez-Camacho, Miriam; Rojo Arribas, Itziar; Román Molina, Alvaro; Rubio Rubio, Francisco Ignacio; Ruiz López, Eva María; Ruiz Lozano, Francisca; Ruiz Román, Andrea; Salar Pomares, Jose Luis; Salha Pla, Daniel; Sampelayo Condado, Rodrigo; Sánchez Aguilar, Mar; Sánchez de la Cruz, María Teresa; Sánchez Gutiérrez, Eva; Sánchez Martínez, Rafael; Sánchez Riquelme, Marina; Sanz Sahagun, Blanca; Seva Compañy, Estrella; Sohm, Amanda; Sohoreanu, Alexandra; Soler Miret, María Victòria; Soler Vicente, Cristina; Soriano Balcázar, Antonio; Taverner Caselles, Elisa; Valero García, Noelia; Vañó Belda, María José; Verdú Pérez, Lorena; Verdú Sala, María Cristina; Vidal de la Peña Solis, Gabriela; Zarco Llorens, Claudia.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjmed.2024.107885>.

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